

Photochemistry of Cobalt(III) Complexes in Aerosol OT/Water/Heptane Microemulsion System

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Manuscript received 10 February 1993

A photochemical reaction conducted in reverse micellar media is influenced by the environment which results in control and/or modification of reactivity. The ability of the reverse micelle to solubilise a large amount of water is a distinguishing feature. The salient features of these micelles, where aggregation occurs in an inverted manner that influences the photochemical reactivity, are microviscosity effects, localisation and cage effects.

Three cobalt(III) complexes have been studied at a fixed pH at two different wavelengths 254 and 313 nm in different pool-sizes. The photoredox quantum yield $\Phi_{Co^{2+}}$ at both the wavelengths decreases with the decrease of wavelength of the photolysis radiation in all the three pool-sizes studied, in the same manner as observed in pure aqueous media.

A distinguishing feature of the inverted micelle where aggregation occurs in an inverted manner, is their ability to solubilise large amount of water in the inner-polar core¹. The size of the water-pool is controlled by the surfactant to water ratio and is very much independent of the nonpolar solvent and the concentration of the surfactant. The photochemistry of three cobalt(III) complexes $[Co(NH_3)_5HC_2O_4](ClO_4)_2$, $[Co(en)_2(aniline)Cl](ClO_4)_2$ and $[Co(NH_3)_5Br]Br_2$ has been studied by us at a fixed pH and at two different wavelengths, viz. 254 and 313 nm in water-pools of different sizes and also with the addition of ethylene glycol.

Results and Discussion

From the results (Table 1) we find that $\Phi_{Co^{2+}}$ in reverse micelles is reduced compared to aqueous media in cases of all the three complexes at both the wavelengths. The maximum retardation in $\Phi_{Co^{2+}}$ yield is observed with lowest amount of water when the water is believed to be highly structured. The greatest percentage decrease in the smallest water-pool has been observed with the bromo-complex. The order of percentage decrease

is : bromo complex > *cis*-chloro(aniline)-bis-ethylenediamine complex > oxalato complex. With the addition of ethylene glycol we have observed two different kinds of effects. In the oxalate and *cis*-chloro(aniline)-bis-ethylenediaminecobalt(III) complexes, the addition of ethylene glycol in the largest size water-pool has increased the $\Phi_{Co^{2+}}$ compared to that without ethylene glycol. Similar increase was also observed with pure aqueous media². But with $[Co(NH_3)_5Br]Br_2$, we noticed a decrease in $\Phi_{Co^{2+}}$ compared with that in the largest size water-pool, without the additive.

Before proceeding for a discussion of the effect of microheterogeneous medium it would be better to present a brief quantitative model of the microemulsion³. A W/O microemulsion is a thermodynamically stable, isotropic, transparent liquid dispersion of small spherical droplets (~10 nm) surrounded by a monomolecular layer of surfactant molecules in a continuous oil phase. The molar concentration ratio of water and surfactant (W_0) determines the radius of the droplets.

Each water spherule, of radius R_w (Fig. 1) is surrounded by n_a molecules of AOT (diisooctyl-

TABLE 1—PHOTOLYSIS OF Co^{III} COMPLEXES ENGAGED IN THE INNER WATER-CORE OF INVERTED MICELLE OF AOT-WATER-HEPTANE SYSTEM AT 35°

$\Phi_{\text{Co}^{2+}}$ as a function of water content in AOT-Water-Heptane System

Compd.	Excitation wavelength nm	Concn. of complex mol dm^{-3}	Medium	Microenvironment	Water content % (v/v)	$\Phi_{\text{Co}^{2+}}$			
<i>cis</i> -[Co(en) ₂ .(C ₆ H ₅ NH ₂)Cl](ClO ₄) ₂	254	1×10^{-4}	AOT-water-heptane	Inner core containing 0.01 N HClO ₄	2.00	0.051			
					2.8	0.062			
					4.0	0.065			
							Inner core containing 50% (v/v) ethylene glycol 0.02 N HClO ₄	2.0	0.077
							0.01 N HClO ₄	Homogeneous (bulk aq. phase)	100
			50% (v/v) ethylene glycol 0.02 N HClO ₄	Homogeneous	50	0.112 (20% increase)			
<i>cis</i> -[Co(en) ₂ .(C ₆ H ₅ NH ₂)Cl](ClO ₄) ₂	313	1×10^{-4}	AOT-water-heptane	Inner core containing 0.01 N HClO ₄	2.0	0.037			
					2.8	0.046			
					4.0	0.049			
<i>cis</i> -[Co(en) ₂ .(C ₆ H ₅ NH ₂)Cl](ClO ₄) ₂	313	1×10^{-4}	0.01 N HClO ₄	50% ethylene glycol-0.02 N HClO ₄	2.0	0.065			
					100	0.055			
					Homogeneous bulk aq. phase	50	0.054		
[Co(NH ₃) ₅ .(HC ₂ O ₄)](ClO ₄) ₂	254	1×10^{-4}	AOT-water-heptane	Inner core containing acetic acid-acetate buffer at pH 4.63	2.0	0.31			
					2.8	0.33			
					4.0	0.35			
					50% (v/v) ethylene glycol-acetic acid acetate buffer pH 4.63	2.0	0.46		
					Acetic acid-acetate buffer at pH 4.63	Homogeneous (bulk aq. phase)	100	0.42	
		50% (v/v) ethylene glycol-acetic acid-acetate buffer pH 4.63	Homogeneous	50	0.48 (14% increase)				
[Co(NH ₃) ₅ .HC ₂ O ₄](ClO ₄) ₂	313	2×10^{-4}	AOT-water heptane	Inner core containing acetic acid-acetate buffer pH 4.63	2.0	0.166			
					2.8	0.179			
					4.0	0.188			
					50% (v/v) ethylene glycol-acetic acid-acetate buffer pH 4.63	2.0	0.220		
					Acetic acid-acetate buffer at pH 4.63	Homogeneous (bulk aq. phase)	100	0.205	
		50% (v/v) ethylene glycol-acetic acid-acetate buffer at pH 4.63	Homogeneous	50	0.225 (10% increase)				

Table-1 (Contd.)

[Co(NH ₃) ₅ Br]Br ₂	254	1×10 ⁻⁴	AOT-water-heptane	Inner core containing	2.0	0.148	
				acetic acid-acetate buff-	2.8	0.181	
				er at pH 4.63	4.0	0.192	
				50% (v/v) ethylene gly-	2.0	0.172	
				col-acetic acid-acetate			
				buffer at pH 4.63			
[Co(NH ₃) ₅ Br].Br ₂	254	1×10 ⁻⁴	Acetic acid-acetate	Homogeneous (bulk aq.	100	0.33	
				buffer at pH 4.63	phase)		
			50% (v/v) ethylene	Homogeneous	50	0.30 (9%	
			glycol-acetic acid-ace-			decrease)	
			tate buffer at pH				
			4.63				
[Co(NH ₃) ₅ Br].Br ₂	313	2×10 ⁻⁴	AOT-water-heptane	Inner core containing	2.0	0.140	
				acetic acid-acetate buff-	2.8	0.177	
				er at pH 4.63	4.0	0.188	
					50% (v/v) ethylene gly-	2.0	0.158
					col-acetic acid-acetate		
			buffer at pH 4.63				
		2×10 ⁻⁴	Acetic acid acetate	Homogeneous (bulk aq.	100	0.24	
			buffer at pH 4.63	phase)			
			50% (v/v) Ethylene	Homogeneous	50	0.21	
			glycol-acetate buffer			(11.8% de-	
			at pH 4.63			crease)	

Fig. 1. Model of micro-emulsion (W/O).

sulphosuccinate) accompanying an average interfacial area $A = 65 \text{ \AA}^2$. The ionic SO_3^- groups (molecular volume $v_s = 50 \text{ \AA}^3$) will be assumed to be in the water phase and may donate their Na^+ counter ions to that phase. For a microemulsion system composed of W_0 water molecules (molecular volume $v_w = 30 \text{ \AA}^3$) per AOT molecules we have

$$n_a A = 4\pi R_w^2 \text{ (area)} \quad (1)$$

$$n_a(W_0 v_w + v_s) = \frac{4}{3}\pi R_w^3 \text{ (volume)} \quad (2)$$

The volume of Na^+ ion has been neglected.

From equations (1) and (2) we have

$$R_w = (3/\text{\AA}) (W_0 v_w + v_s) = (1.4W_0 + 2.3) \text{ \AA}$$

$$\text{and } n_a = 4\pi R_w^2 / A = 0.19 R_w^2 / \text{\AA}^2$$

The R_p (outer radius of the particle) is given by $R_p = R_w + L$, where L is the length of AOT molecule without the SO_3^- group ($L = 10.5 \text{ \AA}$). L_1 is the length of the apolar part of the AOT molecule, $L_1 = 7.5 \text{ \AA}$. The shaded area (Fig. 1) indicates the polar part.

The values of R_w , n_a , R_p and the number of free molecules etc. for our W/O microemulsion systems in three different pool-sizes are shown in Table 2.

The volume fraction Φ_p of the droplets is obtained from the volume fraction Φ_w of water. The latter quantity can be calculated from the weighed amounts of AOT, water and heptane used to form the mi-

TABLE 2—QUANTITATIVE MODEL FOR THE MICROEMULSION WITH AOT-WATER-HEPTANE IN DIFFERENT [WATER]/[SURFACTANT] RATIOS

$W_o =$ Water AOT in molar concn.	R_w Å	$R_p =$ ($R_w + L$) Å	a No. of AOT molecules in the pool	No. of water molecules in the pool	Water molecules bound to AOT $n_a \times 6$	No. of free water molecules	Total no. of water molecules free water molecule	Φ_w	Φ_p
11.5	18.40	28.9	64.33	739.80	386.00	353.00	2.09	0.020	0.088
16.0	24.70	35.2	116.00	1 856.00	696.00	1 160.00	1.60	0.029	0.092
23.1	34.77	45.2	228.00	5 266.00	1 368.00	3 898.00	1.35	0.040	0.130

croemulsion.

We now have³

$$\Phi_p = \left(1 + \frac{L}{R_w}\right)^3 \Phi_w \left(\frac{W_o v_w + v_s}{W_o v_w}\right)$$

The various values are given in Table 2.

Several physical properties (and also our findings as presented in Table 2) have clearly indicated the change in properties of the water core as a function of the ratio of water to AOT. At very low water content there is an increase in the polarity of the core and most of the molecules of water are utilised to form the hydration sphere of the surfactant head groups or counterions (about 4 to 6 water molecules per head of AOT) and hence the inner core is very viscous (as is evident from Table 2). The water molecules not involved in hydration are still involved in some bonding interactions like hydrogen bonding or other ion-dipole interaction with the sulphonate or carboxylic group of AOT molecules present in the cavity⁴. The ionic substrate may be presumably located near the interface region due to electrostatic effects and in the inner core, due to decrease in free water content (Table 2), the local concentration of the solutes will be high. As a result, deactivation of the excited states of the solute through more effective dissipation via large AOT molecules are more probable.

In larger water-pools (as is evident from Table 2), there are more free water molecules so that water properties can resemble that of ordinary/bulk water. As mentioned earlier, our results show a decrease in $\Phi_{Co^{2+}}$ value as a function of water content. The substrate present in the water pools of reverse micelle exchanges freely with other water-

pools through intermicellar collisions⁵ which enhance the possibility of deactivation of the excited probe with an unexcited one. A transient dimer model for the coalescing water droplets was proposed with the opening of a water channel at the point of collision through which diffusion-controlled exchange or migration of solute has been pictured to take place. This water droplet collision and solute exchange process are believed to be very rapid⁶. With increasing water content the micellar size increases resulting in the variation of core fluidity which reduces the probability of probe-deactivator encounter. This is obvious from the greater value of $\Phi_{Co^{2+}}$ in bigger sizes of the pool in all the three Co^{III} complexes. Moreover, the Co^{III} complexes with organic ligands can orient themselves in the inverted micelles in such a manner that the organic ligands go inside the oil phase and the inorganic metallic part rests at the interface which can be spatially more suitable for collisional deactivation. The decrease in $\Phi_{Co^{2+}}$ in micellar media with respect to water in case of *cis*-[Co(en)₂(aniline)Cl](ClO₄)₂ is quite high which can be explained on the basis of specific orientation along the oil phase.

The $\Phi_{Co^{2+}}$ value in aqueous media in case of the bromo complex is less than that of the oxalato complex. Although oxalate radical reduction of the oxalato complex is very efficient⁷ as has been traditionally assumed, the photoreduction of the Co-oxalato complex has been found to proceed through a long-lived metastable intermediate that decays relatively slowly into $\Phi_{Co^{2+}}$ and some oxalate radical⁸ thereby producing an overall higher value of $\Phi_{Co^{2+}}$ compared to those of the other two Co-complexes studied.

The lower value of $\Phi_{Co^{2+}}$ in aqueous media

for the bromo complex could be due to several factors like the binding energy of the CTTM (charge transfer to metal) excited state which restricts the diffusive separation of the radical species and also may be the standard reduction potential of the Br_2/Br^- . As the SRP of Br_2/Br^- (2.09) is higher than that of the oxalate/ Co_2 (1.35 V) system, the tendency of Co^{3+} to be reduced by Br^- would be lower. This reduction effect in case of the bromo complex is further favoured in the reverse micellar media.

Cage-effect : The reduced quantum yield compared to aqueous media can also be explained by enhanced cage-effect, which happens due to the architecture of the reverse micelles. The probe molecules in the small water-pools experience microviscosity and the radical pairs formed cannot diffuse away from each other spending longer time in the restricted space.

Excitation of the complex to its singlet excited state is normally followed by a radiationless transition to a lower lying triplet state,

The latter undergoes homolytic cleavage to produce a geminate triplet radical pair in the solvent cage (in this case small water-pool). The triplet radical pair can also undergo a change in spin angular momentum to form a singlet radical pair and the 1R_p can undergo a recombination process to regenerate the original substrate. In pure aqueous media the formation of free radicals occurs very rapidly on a time-scale too short to allow the ISC (intersystem crossing) to happen. Thus for ISC to take place we need to preserve the super-cage environment. In the reverse micelles the small water-pools with rigidity in the core can provide a super-cage environment thus favouring the radical pair recombination.

Effect of additives : As mentioned earlier, additive like ethylene glycol (50%, v/v) in the largest water-pools behaves differently in different Co^{III} complexes. In case of $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Br}]\text{Br}_2$, addition of ethylene glycol reduces $\Phi_{\text{Co}^{2+}}$ in the largest studied water-pool.

The viscosity effect in this particular case has enhanced the radical pair recombination process due to restricted movement as expected⁹, whereas in the other two complexes the presence of organic solvent in water-pool has led to higher $\Phi_{\text{Co}^{2+}}$ value. The increased value suggests that while viscosity is a factor in reducing the quantum yield, it is not always so in the overall photochemical processes and some other effects, viz. rate constants for non-radiative decay processes may be different on changing the solvent or there may be a low energy onset of a CTTM state corresponding to oxidation of solvent in some cases of the Co^{III} complexes. Owing to selective solvation effects in mixed solvent media even in reverse micelle, one might expect thermodynamic enthalpy of forming radical pair to vary strongly with solvent composition and this effect should contribute to the binding of the CTTM excited state.

Ratios of $\Phi_{\text{Co}^{2+}}$ at two wave lengths : The ratios of $\Phi_{\text{Co}^{2+}}$ at 254 and 313 nm in pure aqueous media are greater than the ratios of $\Phi_{\text{Co}^{2+}}$ in three different pool-sizes (Table 3). There is a slight increase in the ratio in the smallest pool-size in all the three complexes which could be due to concentration effect. The decrease in the ratios may be indicative of the fact that the rigid structure inside the inner core does not allow the radical pairs to diffuse away easily thereby requiring a larger amount of energy to do so. As a result, the radical pair recombination process is encouraged which is reflected in the reduced value of ratios of quantum yields ($\Phi_{\text{Co}^{2+}}$) at the two wavelengths.

Experimental

The complexes $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{HC}_2\text{O}_4]^{2+}(\text{ClO}_4)_2$, $[\text{Co}(\text{en})_2(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NI}_2)\text{Cl}]^{2+}(\text{ClO}_4)_2$ and $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Br}]^{2+}\text{Br}_2$ were all prepared according to the methods reported in literature¹⁰.

The purity of all the samples was checked by chemical analysis and by the uv-visible spectra. The photolysis of the complexes was carried out at 254 and 313 nm radiations. The 313 nm radiations were generated from a H_4 - lamp (General Electric)

TABLE 3-RATIOS OF $\Phi_{Co^{2+}}$ AT 254 AND 313 nm OF Co^{III} COMPLEXES IN AQUEOUS MEDIA AND IN INVERTED MICELLES OF AOT-WATER-HEPTANE IN DIFFERENT POOL SIZES

Compd.	Medium	Micro-environment	Water content	$[H_2O]/[AOT]$ in molar %	$\frac{\Phi_{Co^{2+}} \text{ at } 254 \text{ nm}}{\Phi_{Co^{2+}} \text{ at } 313 \text{ nm}}$ concn.
Cis [Co(en) ₂ (C ₆ H ₅ NH ₂)Cl](ClO ₄) ₂	0.01 N HClO ₄	Homogeneous (bulk aq. phase)	100	—	1.69
	AOT-water-heptane	0.01 N HClO ₄	2.0	11.50	1.38
	AOT-water-heptane	0.01 N HClO ₄	2.8	16.00	1.35
	AOT-water-heptane	0.01 N HClO ₄	4.0	23.08	1.33
[Co(NH ₃) ₅ . HC ₂ O ₄]. (ClO ₄) ₂	Acetic acid-acetate buffer at pH 4.63	Homogeneous	100	—	2.04
	AOT-water-heptane	Inner core containing acetic acid-acetate buffer	2.0	11.50	1.87
			2.8	16.00	1.84
			4.0	23.08	1.86
[Co(NH ₃) ₅ Br]. Br ₂	Acetic acid-acetate buffer at pH 4.63	Homogeneous	100	—	1.38
	AOT-water-heptane	Inner core containing acetic acid - acetate buffer at pH 4.63	2.0	11.50	1.057
			2.8	16.00	1.022
			4.0	23.08	1.021

and 254 nm radiations from a low pressure mercury vapour lamp (Thermal Syndicate T/M5/594-110 W). The 313 nm radiations were isolated from the radiations of the medium pressure lamp by using potassium chromate (0.27 g + 1.0 g Na₂CO₃ per dm⁻³) filter in conjunction with chances 0-0 glass filter. The AOT (diisooctylsulphosuccinate) which was used for the reverse micelle, was dissolved in n-heptane (redistilled) to make a 0.1 M. solution with respect to AOT. The water-pool size was varied by adding different amounts of water (Na-acetate-acetic acid buffer at pH 4.63). For studies with mixed solvent (aquo-organic) pool, ethylene glycol was mixed (50% v/v) with aqueous layer. The AOT solution and the aqueous layer were mixed thoroughly and left for quite some time for getting the reverse micelle of W/O type.

The photolysis was carried out in quartz vessel. The temperature of the system was maintained at 35° throughout by circulating water from a Universal Thermostat (U3). The lamp output was observed before and after the experiment using ferrioxalate

actinometry¹¹. The photoreleased Co²⁺ ion was estimated by Kitson's method¹².

Acknowledgement

Thanks are due to Prof. Sukumar Aditya for initiating us in the field of photochemistry and to the Department of Chemical Technology, University of Calcutta, for laboratory facilities.

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